

Assessment of mammalian diversity and human mammalian interaction in Chikar, Azad Jammu And Kashmir, Pakistan

Urooj Jahanghir¹ and Maryam Faiz^{1*}

1. Department of Women University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Bagh, Pakistan

*Corresponding author e-mail: maryamfaiz1996@gmail.com

SUMMARY

There are 4763 species of mammals in the world. Pakistan has three bio-geographic areas, namely Palearctic, Oriental, and Ethiopian, and hence exhibits a unique combination of floral and faunal richness. Pakistan's mammalian fauna includes 195 species. The country has 225 wetlands, and sudden height variations cause changes in variety within short distances. The research's main goals were to analyze the mammalian diversity of the study region and human contact with species of mammals. The linear count approach was used to estimate mammalian diversity using direct and indirect counts. The direct count is higher than the indirect count. Ethno-mammalian data, such as respondent profiles and human-mammalian interactions, were gathered using a questionnaire. Throughout the study, 15 species of mammals were examined, as well as Shannon-wiener Index was -1.097624028. It is found that the area has a diverse range of animals. Humans have extensive relationship with animals, which are also employed for therapeutic uses.

Keywords: Mammals, Zoology, Wildlife, Human, Animals

Citation: Jahanghir, U., M. Faiz. 2022. Assessment of mammalian diversity and human mammalian interaction in Chikar, Azad Jammu And Kashmir, Pakistan. International Journal of Forest Sciences. 2: 175-181.

Received: October, 2022; **Accepted:** December, 2022

INTRODUCTION

Terrestrial species, such as mammals, are significant environmental indications that assist to identify priority conservation sites. Metrics like the species richness now occupying a specific area, migration, and the degree of risk to the taxa assist in conservation programs. Temperature changes interrupt hibernation, diminish water availability in desert regions, cause extreme weather events, and transmit infections, all of which have an impact on mammalian species (Myers, 1990; Myers *et al.*, 2000; Garcia-Solache and Casadevall, 2010; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020). Precipitation decreases have been linked to declines in numerous big animal species. Precipitation decreases plant development and increases predation threats (Ogutu and Owen-Smith, 2003; Musiega and Kazadi, 2004).

The habitat preferences of species must be examined in order to comprehend diversity trends. Certain mammalian species prefer to live near people, while others prefer partially or fully disturbed ecosystems (Bateman and Fleming, 2012; Riem *et al.*, 2012; Ijaz and Adil, 2021; Altaf *et al.*, 2022; Aslam *et al.*, 2022). Anthropogenic factors have a significant impact on species of mammals, with some adapting to their

surroundings whereas others declining and becoming extinct (Recher, 1999). For the previous 10,000 years, natural ecosystems have been degraded and turned into agricultural fields. Nevertheless, agricultural intensification began towards the end of the twentieth century, resulting in a confrontation among wildlife and people (Bouma and Droogers, 1998; Pimentel *et al.*, 2004; Henle *et al.*, 2008). While greater agricultural land yields and increased farming activity are critical, species protection is also critical. People present nearly all sorts of landscapes, and their importance in protection cannot be overstated (Henle *et al.*, 2008).

Ethnomammalogy explores community knowledge about mammals; the branch of inquiry can help conservation efforts by increasing information about local variety. For species conservation, local people's knowledge and the diversity of urban and rural locations must be examined. Unfortunately, these studies are underutilized, and relatively few scientists in Pakistan focused on this topic during their research (Alves and Souto, 2015; Abbasi, 2021; Haidar, 2021; Ijaz and Adil, 2021; Riaz and Altaf, 2021; Aslam *et al.*, 2022).

The mammals' variety is constantly threatened by the negative consequences of urbanization, which has resulted in the segmentation of larger habitats, pollution, and altered natural climatic patterns. Similarly, unlawful hunting and the utilization of mammalian body parts in medicine drove several species to extinction. The current study is thus organised with the following goals in mind: to quantify mammalian diversity and to investigate the amount of human-mammal relationship in the Chikar.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DESCRIPTION ABOUT AREA OF STUDY

Data collected from Chakar, Hattian Bala. The total population of district Chakkar (Hattian Bala) is about 230529. The temperature of Hattian Bala is moderate as shown in Figure 1.

MAMMALIAN DIVERSITY STUDY

The linear count approach was used to estimate mammalian diversity using direct as well as indirect observations. The direct observation (physical presence and voices) is more accurate than the indirect observation (nests, pug marks, marks, group meetings and individual meetings). With the help of Binoculars and field guides, mammals (Roberts, 2005a, b; Mirza and Wasiq, 2007) were identify.

ETHNO-MAMMALIAN STUDY

The data were gathered through questions and meetings i.e. the profile of the respondents and human mammalian interaction.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Shannon diversity (H') was observed with the help of formula as written below

$$H' = -[\sum P_i \ln P_i]$$

Where H'=Diversity Index

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data collected from male (54) and female (46). All are Muslim. Data collected from different people of Chakar, Hattian Bala and education of people is Illiterate (28), Primary (15), Middle (14), Metric (15), F.A (10) B.A (8) and M.A (3), B.Sc. (3) B.Com (4). Data collected from people of Chakar, Hattian Bala of cast of Mughal (15), Sayeed (11), Meer (15), Qurashi (18), Raja (20), Khawaja (12) and Chadury (9). Data collected from Unemployed (19), Government employer (8), Labour (9), Driver (8), Cook (5), mechanic (4), student (8) teacher (6) and housewife (18) Army (2), Shopkeeper (11) and Engineer (2) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Profile of the informants of the Chakar, Hattian Bala.

Total 15 mammalian species was observed during the research and Shannon-wiener Index was as -1.097624028. House shrew is seen from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as RA=0.039841. Cape hare is observed from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as R.A. 0.01992. Small Kashmir flying squirrel is observed from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as (0.079681). Indian crested porcupine is seen from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as (R.A=0.099602). Grey langur is observed from the Chakar, Hattian Bala (0.007968). Small Indian is observed from Chakar, Hattian Bala (0.0119520), common palm civet is observed from Chakar, Hattian Bala (R.A. =0.0039841). Soft-furred field rat is seen from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as (0.10757). House rat is seen from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as (0.039841). House mouse is seen from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as (0.007968). Rhesus is observed from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as (0.115538); Asiatic Jackal is observed from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as (0.14741); Indian wild boar is

seen from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as 0.079681, small Indian mongoose is observed from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as 0.11952., Himalayan palm civet is observed from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as 0.007968. Bengal fox is seen from the Chakar, Hattian Bala as (0.04382). The diversity indices reveals that the diversity of indices of mammalian diversity of Chakar, Hattian Bala is observed as species (18), individual (251) and Shannon (1.097624028) in table 1.

Table 1: Mammalian diversity of the Chakar, Hattian Bala.

Common name	Scientific name	RA/Pi	LogPi	PiLogPi
Small Kashmir Flying Squirrel	<i>Holopetes fimriatus</i>	0.079681	-1.098645224	-0.08754115
Small Indian Mongoose	<i>Herpestes auropunctatus</i>	0.119522	-0.922552148	-0.110265278
Small Indian civet	<i>Vevirricula indica</i>	0.011952	-1.922559416	-0.02297843
Rhesus Macaque	<i>Maccaca multatta</i>	0.115538	-0.937275155	-0.108290897
Red Fox	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	0.043825	-1.358278075	-0.059526537
Indian Wild Boar	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	0.079681	-1.098645224	-0.08754115
Indian Crested Porcupine	<i>Hystrix Porcupine</i>	0.099602	-1.001731941	-0.099774505
House Shrew	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	0.039841	-1.399669769	-0.055764243
House Rat	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	0.039841	-1.399669769	-0.055764243
House mouse	<i>Mus musculus</i>	0.007968	-2.098650675	-0.016722049
Himalayan Palm civet	<i>Paguma larvata</i>	0.007968	-2.098650675	-0.016722049
Grey langur	<i>Semnopithecus entellus</i>	0.007968	-2.098650675	-0.016722049
Common palm civet	<i>Paradoxurus hermaphrodotus</i>	0.003984	-2.39968067	-0.009560328
Cape hare	<i>Lepus Capensis</i>	0.01992	-1.700710666	-0.033878156
Asiatic Jackal	<i>Canus aureus</i>	0.14741	-0.831473054	-0.122567443
Shannon wiener diversity Index		1.097624028		

During the research noted that different species of mammals used for different diseases as; meat of cape hare is used against paralysis and joint pain. Fat of small Kashmir flying squirrel is used to treatment of joint pain. House shrew is used for the treatment of cow pox disease. Indian crested porcupine' meat is used for Joint pain and calcium deficiency, Asiatic jackal are used against pain. Small Indian Mongoose bones are used joint pain and snake bite. Fats of Fat of Bengal fox are used for epilepsy.

During the research noted that different species of mammals used for different diseases as; meat of cape hare is used against Paralysis, joint pain; small Kashmir flying squirrel (urine) is used for the treatment of constipation; house shrew (bones) is used for the treatment of cow pox disease; Indian crested porcupine used for joint pain and calcium deficiency; Asiatic jackal (Fats) used against pain; small Indian mongoose (bones) is used against pain; Bengal Fox (Fat) is used for epilepsy, Himalayan palm civet (bile) is used for treatment of paralysis. While previously documented of these mammals for medicine as; asthma, sciatica, arthritis, gout,

paralysis, sciatica, arthritis, body pain. Fat and meat are used by the people of Chakar and Hattian Bala to heal skin disorders, joint problems, burning, bodily swelling, and as a libido enhancer. The presence of omega-3 fatty acid in fat, which decreases inflammatory, might be used to cure human illnesses. This chemical is also beneficial in neurological disorders, atherosclerosis, thrombosis, and ageing (Breteler, 2000; Kalmijn, 2000; Haag, 2003; Wilson, 2015). This might be attributed to milk's rich lipid, mineral, protein, and vitamin content, which strengthens the body, reduces joint discomfort, and improves associated with sex potency (Hemme *et al.*, 2010; Alabdulkarim, 2012; Sabahelkhier *et al.*, 2012; Contarini and Povolò, 2013; Vats and Thomas, 2015).

Table 2: Ethno-mammalogical study of the Chakar, Hattian Bala.

Common name	Local name	Superstitious	Medicinal use
House shrew	Taluha	No	Cow pox disease.
Cape hare	Sehhya	No	Paralysis and joint pain.
Small Indian mongoose	Noul	No	Joint pain and snake bite.
Small Kashmir Flying Squirrel	Kees	No	Joint pain.
Indian Crested Porcupine	Seggh	If scales of this present any where it cause quarrel	Asthma, joint pain and calcium deficiency.
House Mouse	Choha	If juvenile mouse present in house it cause death.	Wound healing and joints pains.
Asiatic Jackal	Gedhar	No	Pain.
Bengal Fox	Phand	If fox speak any place then cause death	Epilepsy.
Small Indian Civet	Seu trimba	No	Pain.

REFERENCES

- Abbasi, Z. 2021. Diversity and folklore medicinal uses of mammalian species of Harighal, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 60-65.
- Alabdulkarim, B. 2012. Effect of camel milk on blood glucose, cholesterol, triglyceride and liver enzymes activities in female Albino rats. *World Applied Sciences Journal*. 17: 1394-1397.
- Altaf, M., K.J. Iqbal, M.S. Haider, S. Ashraf. 2022. Habitat Preferences of Wild Mammalian Species around River Chenab in Sialkot, Gujrat and Gujranwala Districts, Punjab, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Zoology*. 1-7.
- Alves, R., W.M.S. Souto. 2015. *Ethnozoology: A Brief Introduction*. *Ethnobiology and Conservation*. 4.
- Aslam, H., S. Ashraf, S. Adil. 2022. Human activities impacts on distribution of mammalian species in the vicinity of Uchali complex, Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 6: 111-120.
- Bateman, P., P. Fleming. 2012. Big city life: carnivores in urban environments. *Journal of Zoology*. 287: 1-23.
- Bouma, J., P. Droogers. 1998. A procedure to derive land quality indicators for sustainable agricultural production. *Geoderma*. 85: 103-110.

- Breteler, M.M. 2000. Vascular risk factors for Alzheimer's disease:: An epidemiologic perspective. *Neurobiology of aging*. 21: 153-160.
- Contarini, G., M. Povolo. 2013. Phospholipids in milk fat: composition, biological and technological significance, and analytical strategies. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 14: 2808-2831.
- Garcia-Solache, M.A., A. Casadevall. 2010. Global warming will bring new fungal diseases for mammals. *MBio*. 1: e00061-00010.
- Haag, M. 2003. Essential fatty acids and the brain. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*. 48: 195-203.
- Haidar, R. 2021. Morphological hair identification key of wild mammals in Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 128-134.
- Hemme, T., J. Otte, R. Echeverri Perico, R. Paarlberg, I. Walker, H. Pino, D. Horton, J. Polanía Vorenberg, J. Toro Calderón, C. López Balmaceda. 2010. Status and prospects for smallholder milk production. A global perspective. FAO, Roma (Italia).
- Henle, K., D. Alard, J. Clitherow, P. Cobb, L. Firbank, T. Kull, D. McCracken, R.F. Moritz, J. Niemelä, M. Rebane. 2008. Identifying and managing the conflicts between agriculture and biodiversity conservation in Europe—A review. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*. 124: 60-71.
- Ijaz, S., S. Adil. 2021. Anthropogenic impacts on the distribution of mammalian species in the vicinity of Head Trimmu, Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 168-175.
- Ijaz, S., S. Adil, H. Aslam, R. Kanwal, S. Afsheen. 2020. Human interaction, conflict, threats and role of mammals-A review. *Journal of Ethnomedicine and Ethnoecology*. 1: 1-11.
- Kalmijn, S. 2000. Fatty acid intake and the risk of dementia and cognitive decline: a review of clinical and epidemiological studies. *Journal of Nutrition Health. Aging*. 4: 202-207.
- Mirza, Z.B., H. Wasiq. 2007. A field guide to birds of Pakistan Bookland, Lahore.
- Musiega, D.E., S.N. Kazadi. 2004. Simulating the East African wildebeest migration patterns using GIS and remote sensing. *African Journal of Ecology*. 42: 355-362.
- Myers, J.H., D. Simberloff, A.M. Kuris, J.R. Carey. 2000. Eradication revisited: dealing with exotic species. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*. 15: 316-320.
- Myers, N. 1990. The biodiversity challenge: expanded hot-spots analysis. *Environmentalist*. 10: 243-256.
- Ogutu, J.O., N. Owen-Smith. 2003. ENSO, rainfall and temperature influences on extreme population declines among African savanna ungulates. *Ecology letters*. 6: 412-419.
- Pimentel, D., B. Berger, D. Filiberto, M. Newton, B. Wolfe, E. Karabinakis, S. Clark, E. Poon, E. Abbett, S. Nandagopal. 2004. Water resources: agricultural and environmental issues. *BioScience*. 54: 909-918.
- Recher, H.F. 1999. The state of Australia's avifauna: a personal opinion and prediction for the new millennium. *Australian Zoologist*. 31: 11-27.
- Riaz, T., M. Altaf. 2021. Diversity and cultural uses of mammals in Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 159-167.
- Riem, J.G., R.B. Blair, D.N. Pennington, N.G. Solomon. 2012. Estimating mammalian species diversity across an urban gradient. *The American Midland Naturalist*. 168: 315-332.
- Roberts, T.J. 2005a. Field guide to the large and medium-sized mammals of Pakistan. Oxford University Press.
- Roberts, T.J. 2005b. Field guide to the small mammals of Pakistan. Oxford University Press.

- Sabahelkhier, M., M. Faten, F. Omer. 2012. Comparative Determination of Biochemical Constituents between Animals (Goat, Sheep, Cow and Camel) Milk with Human Milk. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*. 1: 69-71.
- Vats, R., S. Thomas. 2015. A study on use of animals as traditional medicine by Sukuma Tribe of Busega District in North-western Tanzania. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*. 11: 1.
- Wilson, L. 2015. *Fats and oils for optimum health*. The Center for Development.